

A Study on Growth of Indian Corporate Sectors - A Paradigm Shift to Entrepreneurial Development in India

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Abstract

This study mainly investigates that total number of companies registered and active companies in top ten states and Union territories wise, share capital Range wise, economic activity wise, one person company(OPCs) wise and foreign companies wise as on 30.06.2018 in India. The research study is explorative in nature and will be based on in-depth analysis of data and statistics, composed in the various secondary data. This research used descriptive statistical tools such as percentage analysis, tables, and charts are used for analysis and interpretation of data.

The results of research study indicated that total number of companies registered and active companies 17, 79,761 and 11, 89,826. Out of them 71,506 were public, 11,10,371 were private including 18,153 one person companies. Maximum of registered and active companies are in Maharashtra, Delhi and west Bengal. Highest of active companies are in services sectors (65%) and industry sectors (31%). Total numbers of one person companies (OPC) 18,153 were recorded in India with share capital of Rs.461.06 Crores. In case of foreign companies totally registered 4,678 out of this 3,379 out of which 3,379 companies are functioning as on 30.06.2108. This study finally suggested that government of India, State/ Union governments, policy makers and other regulators agencies should improve existing and create new infrastructure in easy doing business indicators for Indian and foreign investors on regulation for starting a business like land acquisition, dealing with various laws permits, getting electricity and manpower, registering property, getting loans, subsidies, interest free loans and advance, protecting investors investments, improving various direct and indirect tax management system.

Key words: MCA21, Company, Investments, Corporate Governance, OPC

Introduction

The history of corporate laws is ages old in India & dates back to the time of Cholas & Patliputra who were patrons of trade. The concept of corporate form was brought in for first time in United Kingdom wherein by the body corporate could be brought into existence either by a royal charters or by a special act of parliaments. The earliest type of associations indentified as “companies” were they doing the international trade in India the most

famous is the East India Company, Which was chartered by Queen Elisabeth in 1600. The history and development of company Act in India is closely related with that of England. During the British colonial period, Indian companies were controlled by British rules and regulations. Company law in India, as indicated earlier, is the cherished child of English parents born and brought up in England.

Many countries company laws have been shaped

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and brought up from English companies Laws. In India company law made a first appearance in 1850 when a law for registration of joint stock companies was passed and implemented by British government in India. Thereafter consolidation attempt was executed in India in the form of company law 1882 for incorporate the various amendments in the British company law legislation in the early 1860 in order to applicable to the Indian context. Company law 1882 has five different sets of amendments were enacted until first decade of 21st century. Then, British companies' laws consolidation acts 1908, a new legislation was passed in India in the form of company law, 1913.

Companies Act 1956

The company law 1956, had been passed with the main objectives of strengthen and modify the laws relating to companies and certain other associations registered in India. The company law 1956 was implemented in India on 01-04-1956. This law has been in force in past 55 years and amended were made in 25 times. The registered numbers of companies were increased from 30,000 in 1956 to nearly 8, 00,000 companies functioning as the date. In the past three decades in various innovations and changes were taken in the national and international level in economic, foreign investments, labour laws and regulatory environments. India has also getting dividend for growth of Indian corporate sectors during that period in form of financial incentives and infrastructural development. Financial liberalization and promotion of domestic private, public, governments and foreign investment in infrastructure, a new need has at the present begin the change in the regulatory formation for corporate sector was also reflect on necessary to concentrate on issues in the regulatory harmony, recognition of good corporate practices and technological innovations to be implemented. India has been identified as an important

benefactor to corporate global earnings.

Dr. J JIrani Expert Committee for Companies Act 2013

MCA21 is an innovative technology oriented e-governance project initiated by government of India for various online services for company registration to winding up. It makes that India became globally competitive for entrepreneurship development.

The reconsideration of company law 1956 was continued on the basis of board based consultative process of recommendations of company law expert committee was formed 02-12-2004 under the chairmanship of Dr.J.J. Irani, director, Tata Sons. The committee submitted its report to the government of India on 31-05-2005. The new Indian company law beginning in the birth towards modernizing India's company act and bring in the support of global standards. This report was laying foundation for new company law 2013 in India. Company law bill 2012 was passed in the Lok Sabha on 18-12-2012 and the Rajya Sabha passed on 08-08-2013 would be remembered as historic day in the history of corporate India and brings to modernized company law to India. The Company law bill, 2012 was assented, to by the president of India on 29.08.2013 and notified in the Gazette of India on 30.08.2013. It finally became the companies Act 2013.

Review of literature

Cs. Mala Kumari Upadhyay (2017), indicated that the company law 2013 included in various new innovative sections for introduced to growth of business reconstructions process for Indian companies with other foreign companies.

Stephanie (2013), found that the implementation of MCA's E-governance and XBRL implementation achieved immediate benefits.

Rajeshwari M. Shettar (2017), concluded that, make in India force a radical revolution in services sectors, manufacturing sectors and its allied sectors.

Renuka Mahadevan (2003), found that India has effectively utilized the various corporate sectors and economic reforms.

Gyanendra Kumer Sahu (2017), examined earlier corporate law reform in India. This it found that corporate law modification progression was instigated in India to make the lawful structure well-suited with universal standards.

Gupinder Assi, John Welge and Iain Sharp (2013), found the new Indian companies' law 2013 is a constructive movement in the direction of modernizing India's company law and bring into line it to universal standards and introduced safeguard of investors.

Biswatosh Saha (2000), examined pragmatic substantiation of the extensively held existing practice of firm performance in the Indian area. It found that global diversification had an optimistic relation with a firm's market appraisal and firm's ownership composition.

Research Gap

This study has examined many research papers, research studies, research journals, thesis, books, articles, News papers and seminars edited publications relating Indian corporate sectors in India. It helps to identifying the research issues and the research gaps of the present study. There is scarcely little research study carried in India, it shows the trends growth of companies in India especially after major reforms in Indian economy such as impacts of Companies Act 2013, demonetizations and implementations of GST Act 2017 in India. This present study mainly examine

the total numbers of registered companies, States/UTs-wise and sectors wise and trend of registration of Active Companies as on 30.06.2018. In these surroundings the current research diverges from the early researches in numerous ways and contributes the existing literature.

Significance and importance of the study

The Indian corporate sectors have been facing worldwide competition and economic reforms force into various changes in Indian corporate sector. It is needed for major reforms in Indian corporate sector for growth of their economies. In the recent decades India is fast growing economies in developing countries of the world, for creating an environment conducive to many small businesses and bring into financial liberalization. Companies, moved India's business environment towards next stage the companies act is a radical experiment with corporate purpose enacted new company law 2013 is a milestone for passing on valuable investment opportunities are bring into India as an investment destination, choice of location, pricing, employment and all other important policies are centrally decided.

India initiative is getting attention of global investors its progress and success will depend upon ease of doing business in India. Corporate governance issue on implementation of GST reduced the cascading effect of taxes. Corporate governance reform and e-governance initiatives aim to help investors by adding regulatory and judicial to keep on incorporating various governance aspects arising in terms of challenges due to several changes taking place in corporate world. In this background this study mainly focus on total number of companies registered in State/UT-wise, economic activity-number wise and authorized capital of active companies, sectors-wise registered one person company and

investigates the foreign companies as on 30.06.2018.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the total number of private, public, One Person Companies (OPCs) and foreign companies registered and active companies in India as on 30.06.2018
2. To analysis the economic activity wise total number of private, public and One Person Companies (OPCs) in India as on 30.06.2018.
3. To assesses the authorized share capital wise total number of private, public and One Person Companies (OPCs) in India as on 30.06.2018.

Research methodology

The present research study methodology divided into methods data collection and tools used for analysis and interpretation of data. The first segment of deals with the various data collected for the current research study and second segment involves that the various statistical techniques used for the purpose of analyzing and interpretation of data.

Data collection

This study has been carried out descriptive and exploratory nature with the help of the secondary data. The sources include the ministry of corporate affairs reports, RBI monthly bulletins and the RBI annual reports, department of economic affairs, SEBI, DIPP, various central and states ministry reports and economic survey of India. The other sources include various books, working notes, research articles and journals, research magazines, newspapers and websites of state, central governments and related organizations.

Statistical Techniques used

This study has been carried out descriptive and exploratory nature with the help of the secondary data. In order explain the outcome of the study results and interpretations of data by using tables, charts, graphs and descriptive statistical tools of averages and percentages. It covers period of study since with incorporation of Indian Companies Act 2013 up to 30.06.2018.

Results and discussions

Total Number of Registered and active companies in India as on 30.06.2018

1	Companies registered as on 30.06.2018	17,79,761	
2	Number of closed companies	5,43,467	
I	Number of Companies liquidated/Dissolved	10,532	
II	Number of companies Defunct/Struck-off(section 248 of CA,2013)	4,97,742	
III	Number of companies amalgamated /merged	21,367	
IV	Number of companies converted to LLP	9,302	
V	Number of companies converted LLP and dissolved	4,794	
3	Number of companies lying dormant u/s 455 of Companies Act 2013	1,390	
4	Number of companies under liquidation	6,117	
5	Number of companies which are process of section 248 of CA, 2013	38,858	
6	Number of companies Lying AIPG(Active in Progress)	103	
	Number of active companies		11,89,826
	Of which		
	Companies limited by shares		11,81,877
	Company limited by Guarantees		7,518
	Unlimited companies		431

Source: MCA, MIB, June 2018.

The above table 1 clearly detailed that the total number of companies registered as on 30.06.2018 in India shows that 17,79,761. Out of this 5,43,467 companies were closed. Total numbers of companies liquidated and dissolved were in 10,532. Defunct/Struck –off (section 248 of Companies Act 2013) were in India as on 4,97,742. Out of these totally 21,367 companies were amalgamated and merged. Number of companies converted to Limited Liability Partnerships (LLPs) and dissolved 4,794. Total number of companies lying dormant u/s 455 of companies 2013 were in 1,390. Total number of companies under liquidation were 6,117. Numbers of companies which are under process of section 248 of the companies Act, 2013 were in 38,858. Out of these number of companies laying AIPG (Active in progress) were 103. Finally total numbers of active companies as on 30.06.2018 were in 11,89,826. Out of which companies limited by shares were in

11,81,877, companies limited by guarantees were in 7,518 and unlimited companies were in 431.

Top Ten States/UTs wise Total Number of Registered and active companies in India as on 30.06.2018

The below table 2 and chart 1 shows that the top ten states/UTs wise total number of companies registered and active companies in India as on 30.06.2018. This is evident from that above table shows Maharashtra has secured first place in registered most of the companies totally 3,53,556 (20%), it also has maximum number of active companies functioning this state 2,34,151 around (20%). In the second places goes to Delhi has totally registered companies were in 3,22,044 (18%), it's also reflected in the active companies were in 2,16,286 (18%). Third position secured by West Bengal has totally registered companies

1,97,823 (11%), this is also has same position in actives companies were in 1,34,336 (11%). Fourth rank secured by State of Tamil Nadu in total number of registered companies were in 1,36,650 (8%) and active company were in 77,900 (7%). In

the Uttar Pradesh state secured by fifth place for has highest number of registered companies were in 95,546(5%) and also got same position having most of the active companies were in 72,834(6%).

Table 2 Top Ten States/UTs wise total Number of Registered and Active companies India as on 30.06.2018

Sl. No.	State	Registered	Registered (%)	Active	Active (%)
1	Maharashtra	3,53,556	20	2,34,151	20
2	Delhi	3,22,044	18	2,16,286	18
3	West Bengal	1,97,823	11	1,34,336	11
4	Tamil Nadu	1,36,650	8	77,900	7
5	Uttar Pradesh	95,546	5	72,834	6
6	Telangana	98,754	6	71,301	6
7	Karnataka	1,07,424	6	69,615	6
8	Gujarat	96,003	5	63,333	5
9	Rajasthan	54,933	3	37,401	3
10	Kerala	48,253	3	32,277	3
Top 10 states		15,10,986	85	10,09,434	85
Others		2,68,775	15	1,80,392	15
Total		17,79,761	100	11,89,826	100

Source: MCA, MIB, June 2018.

Sixth rank secured by state of Telangana for having maximum number of registered companies were in 98,754 (6%) and active companies were in 72,834 (6%) as on 30.06.2018. In the next position secured by state of Karnataka has more number of registered companies were in 1,07,424 and also in the active companies were in 69,615 (6%). Eighth place secured by state of Gujarat for having maximum number of registered companies 96,003(5%), as well as in the active companies were in 63,333 (5%). In the next position held by state of Rajasthan for having more number of registered companies were in 54,933 (3%) and also having in the active companies were in

37,401(3%). The tenth position held by the state of for having more number of registered companies were in 48,253 (3%) and active companies were in 32,277 (3%) on his state. This results indicated that the top ten states/UTs having 15,10,986 (85%) of the registered companies and 10,09,434 (85%) of the actives companies in India. Others State/UTs are having only 2,68,775 (15%) of the registered companies and also having 1,80,392 (15%) of the active companies. Finally total number of registered companies were in 17,79,761 and active companies were in 11,89,826 as on 30.06.2018 in India.

Chart 1 Top Ten States/UTs wise Total Number of Registered and Active companies in India as on 30.06.2018

Sectors-wise Active Companies as on 30.06.2018

Table 3 Sectors - wise Active Companies as on 30.06.2018

S No	Sectors	Number of Active Companies as on 30 th June, 2018					
		Private	(%)	Public	(%)	Total	(%)
1	Agriculture	31,340	3%	3,015	4%	34,355	3%
2	Industry	3,40,041	30%	27,636	37%	3,67,677	31%
3	Services	7,28,531	65%	40,122	54%	7,68,653	65%
4	Others	15,927	1%	3,214	4%	19,141	2%
	Total	11,15,839	100	73,987	100	11,89,826	100%

Source: MCA, MIB, June 2018.

The above table 3 and chart 2 shows that the sector wise total number of private, public and total active companies as on 30.06.2018. It indicates that highest number of active private companies are in services sectors 7,28,531 (65%), followed by industry sectors (3,40,041) (30%), agriculture sectors (31,340) (3%) and remaining active

companies are in other sectors (15,297) (1%). It shows majority of number of active public companies are in services sectors 40,122 (54%), followed by industry sectors (27,636) (37%), agriculture sectors (3,015) (4%) and remaining active companies are in other sectors (3,214) (4%).

Chart 2 Sectors -wise Number of Active Companies as on 30th June, 2018

It clearly displayed that 65% of total number of active companies are in services sectors 7,68,653, followed by industry sectors (3,67,677) (31%), agriculture sectors (34,355) (3%) and remaining active companies are in other sectors (19,141)(2%).

Sectors -wise active companies authorized capital as on 30.06. 2018

Table 4 Sectors -wise active companies authorized capital (in Rs. Crore) as on 30th June, 2018
 Table 4 Sectors -wise active companies authorized capital (in Rs. Crore) as on 30th June, 2018

S No	Sectors	Active Companies authorized capital (in Rs. Crore)					
		Private	(%)	Public	(%)	Total	(%)
1	Agriculture	23,455.36	1%	34,236.10	1%	57,691.46	1%
2	Industry	10,03,566.18	48%	23,82,958.64	57%	33,86,524.82	54%
3	Services	10,13,873.02	49%	16,57,354.55	39%	26,71,227.57	42%
4	Others	41,955.38	2%	1,39,855.72	3%	1,81,811.10	3%
	Total	20,82,849.94	100	42,14,405.02	100	62,97,254.95	100

Source: MCA, MIB, June 2018.

The above table 4 and chart 3 shows that the sector wise share capital of private, public and total active companies as on 30.06.2018. It explained that most of the private companies authorized capital (in Rs. Crore) are in services sectors (10,13,873.02) (49%), followed by industry sectors (10,03,566.18) (48%), other sectors (41,955.38) (2%) and rest of the active companies are in agriculture sectors

(23,455.36) (1%). It shows that maximum of total number of public active companies authorized capital (in Rs. Crore) are in industry sectors (23,82,958.64) (57%), followed by services sectors (16,57,354.55) (39%), other sectors (1,39,855.72) (3%) and rest of the active companies are in agriculture sectors (34,236.10) (1%). It shows that maximum of total number of

active companies authorized capital (in Rs. Crore) (42%), other sectors (1,81,811.10) (3%) and rest of the active companies are in agriculture sectors (57,691.46) (1%).

Chart 3 Sectors -Wise active companies authorized capital(in Rs. crore) as on 30th June, 2018

Economic activity wise active companies as on 30.06.2018

Table 5 Economic activity wise active companies as on 30.06.2018

S No	Sectors Wise	Number of Active Companies					
		Private		Public		Total	
		Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
1	Business Services	3,59,330	32	11,212	21	3,70,542	31
2	Manufacturing	2,15,688	19	19,935	27	2,35,623	20
3	Trading	1,47,214	13	6,705	15	1,53,919	13
4	Construction	1,00,896	9	5,060	10	1,05,956	9
5	Real Estate and Renting	71,278	6	3,648	7	74,926	6
6	Community & Social Services	67,893	6	4,131	7	72,024	6
7	Finance	48,167	4	12,661	3	60,828	5
8	Transport & Communications	33,907	3	1,592	3	35,499	3
9	Agriculture	31,340	3	3,015	3	34,355	3
10	Others	15,927	1	3,214	1	19,141	2
11	Electricity, Gas & Water	12,250	1	1,829	1	14,079	1
12	Mining & Quarrying	11,207	1	812	1	12,019	1
13	Insurance	742	0	173	1	915	0
Total		11,15,839	100	73,987	100	11,89,826	100

Source: MCA ,MIB June 2018

In the above table 5 shows that economic activity-wise private, public, total number active companies in India as on 30.06.2018. Economic-activity wise Private company wise shows that the Business Services (3,59,330) (32%). Followed by trading (1,47,214) (13%), manufacturing sectors (2,15,688) (19%) and were in others sectors. Economic-activity wise Public company shows that the manufacturing sectors (19,935) (27%). Followed by Business Services (11,212) (21%)

trading (6,705) (15%) and remaining in others sectors. Economic-activity wise total companies shows that the Business Services (3,70,542) (31%). Followed by manufacturing sectors (2,35,623) (20%), trading(1,53,919) (13%) and remaining were in others sectors.

Economic activity wise share capital of active companies as on 30.06.2018

Table 6 Economic activity wise share capital of active companies as on 30.06.2018

S No	Sectors	Authorized Capital					
		Private		Public		Total	
		(in Rs. Crore)	%	(in Rs. Crore)	%	(in Rs. Crore)	%
1	Manufacturing	5,71,638.05	32	9,00,919.16	21	14,72,557.21	23
2	Electricity, Gas	1,66,062.29	19	11,44,326.15	27	13,10,388.43	21
3	Business Services	3,95,582.68	13	6,30,333.60	15	10,25,916.29	16
4	Finance	1,80,955.78	9	4,06,602.68	10	5,87,558.46	9
5	Construction	2,22,094.88	6	2,75,673.06	7	4,97,767.94	8
6	Transport, storage	54,768.91	6	2,81,630.95	7	3,36,399.86	5
7	Trading	2,07,868.96	4	1,11,022.61	3	3,18,891.57	5
8	Community	81,966.53	3	1,37,985.39	3	2,19,951.91	3
9	Others	41,955.38	3	1,39,855.72	3	1,81,811.10	3
10	Real Estate Renting	90,036.06	1	39,419.61	1	1,29,455.67	2
11	Mining & Quarrying	43,770.97	1	62,040.27	1	1,05,811.24	2
12	Agriculture	23,455.36	1	34,236.10	1	57,691.46	1
13	Insurance	2,694.10	0	50,359.71	1	53,053.81	1
Total		20,82,849.94	100	42,14,405.02	100	62,97,254.95	100

Source: MCA, MIB, June 2018.

In the above table 6 explains that economic activity-wise and share capital wise private, public, total number active companies in India as on 30.06.2018. Private company wise, Economic-activity wise, capital wise (in Rs. Crore) shows that the manufacturing sectors (5,71,638.05) (32%). Followed by Electricity, Gas & Water companies (1,66,062.29) (19%), Business Services (3,95,582.68) (13%) and remaining were in others sectors. Public company wise, Economic-activity

wise, capital wise (in Rs. Crore) shows that the manufacturing sectors (9,00,919.16) (21%). Followed by Electricity, Gas & Water companies (11,44,326.15) (27%), Business Services (6,30,333.60) (15%) and remaining were in others sectors. Total companies wise, Economic-activity wise, Share capital (in Rs. Crore) shows that the manufacturing sectors (14,72,557.21) (23%). Followed by Electricity, Gas & Water companies (13,10,388.43) (21%), Business Services

(10,25,916.29) (16%) and remaining were in others sectors.

Authorized Share Capital Range Wise Active Companies in India as on 31.03.2018

Table 7 Authorized Share Capital Range Wise Active Companies in India as on 31.03.2018

S No	Share Capital Range	Private		Public		Total	
		Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
1	Up to 1 lakh	401076	36.66%	3548	4.81%	404624	34.65%
2	Above 1 lakh to 5 lakh	183678	16.79%	11054	14.98%	194732	16.67%
3	Above 5 lakh to 10 lakh	176455	16.13%	7297	9.89%	183752	15.73%
4	Above 10 lakh to 25 lakh	91529	8.37%	6287	8.52%	97816	8.38%
5	Above 25 lakh to 50 lakh	75740	6.92%	5680	7.70%	81420	6.97%
6	Above 50 lakh to 1 crore	61712	5.64%	8001	10.84%	69713	5.97%
7	Above 1 crore to 2 crore	38720	3.54%	5368	7.28%	44088	3.78%
8	Above 2 crore to 5 crore	37277	3.41%	8860	12.01%	46137	3.95%
9	Above 5 crore to 10 crore	12839	1.17%	6306	8.55%	19145	1.64%
10	Above 10 crore to 25 crore	8185	0.75%	5352	7.25%	13537	1.16%
11	Above 25 crore to 100 crore	5019	0.46%	3813	5.17%	8832	0.76%
12	Above 100 crore to 500 crore	1465	0.13%	1385	1.88%	2850	0.24%
13	Above 500 crore to 1000 crore	184	0.02%	256	0.35%	440	0.04%
14	Above 1000 crore	203	0.02%	569	0.77%	772	0.07%
	Total	1094082	100%	73776	100%	1167858	100%

Source : MCA, MIB, March 2018.

In the above table 7 shows that the number of active private, public and total companies in share capital ranges wise in India as on 31.03.2018. Totally 10,94,082 private companies were in India its amounted to 93.68% total companies in India as on 31.03.2018. Out of the private companies 4,01,076 (36.66%) of companies were fallen in the category of up to 1 lakh. Followed by 16.79% of private companies 1, 83,678 were in the group of above one to 5 lakh. This result clearly shows that the more than 75% of private companies fallen share capital range of less than 25 lakh.

Totally 73,776 public companies were in India it's amounted to 6.32% total companies in India as on 31.03.2018. Out of the public companies 11,504 (14.98%) of companies were fallen in the category of above 5 lakh to 10 lakh. Followed by 12.01% of public companies were in the cluster of above 2 Crore to 5 Crores. This result clearly exhibited that

the more than 90% of public companies fallen in the share capital range of less than 25 Crores.

Total number of companies 11,67,858 public companies were in India as on 31.03.2018. Out of the total companies 4,04,624 (34.65%) of companies were fallen in the category of up to 1 lakh. Followed by 16.67% of total companies were in the group of above 1 lakh to 5 lakh. This result clearly indicated that the more than 75% of total companies fallen in group of less than 50 lakh.

Authorized Share Capital Range Wise Active Companies in India as on 31.03.2018

In the below table 8 and chart 4 enlightens that authorized share capital (in Rs. Crore) range wise private, public and total companies wise as on 31.03.2018. In the case total share capital range wise private companies contribution were

20,19,422.67 (Rs in Crores) 33%. Out of this 7,46,030.36 (Rs in Crore) 37% of private companies fallen in the above 1000 crore share capital range. Followed by 316992.82 (Rs in Crores) 16%, 248171.34 (Rs in Crores) 12% of private

companies fallen in share capital range of above 100 Crore to 500 Crores and above 25 Crore to 100 Crores. It's amounted to nearest 65% share capital range and remaining 35% were falls in the other share capital range of private sectors.

Table 8 Authorized Share Capital Range Wise Active Companies in India as on 31.03.2018

S No	Share Capital Range	Private		Public		Total	
		(Rs in Crore)	%	(Rs in Crore)	%	(Rs in Crore)	%
1	Up to 1 lakh	3836.5	0%	11.44	0%	3847.94	0%
2	Above 1 lakh to 5 lakh	7824.19	0%	544.92	0%	8369.11	0%
3	Above 5 lakh to 10 lakh	17360.66	1%	703.51	0%	18064.17	0%
4	Above 10 lakh to 25 lakh	18942.06	1%	1363.61	0%	20305.67	0%
5	Above 25 lakh to 50 lakh	32677.82	2%	2575.01	0%	35252.83	1%
6	Above 50 lakh to 1 crore	54774.74	3%	7516.92	0%	62291.66	1%
7	Above 1 crore to 2 crore	64087.7	3%	9248.05	0%	73335.75	1%
8	Above 2 crore to 5 crore	134696.54	7%	34757.08	1%	169453.62	3%
9	Above 5 crore to 10 crore	100431.41	5%	49953.27	1%	150384.68	2%
10	Above 10 crore to 25 crore	135567.6	7%	91057.58	2%	226625.18	4%
11	Above 25 crore to 100 crore	248171.34	12%	199755.08	5%	447926.43	7%
12	Above 100 crore to 500 crore	316992.82	16%	303469.06	7%	620461.87	10%
13	Above 500 crore to 1000 crore	138028.93	7%	202681.46	5%	340710.4	6%
14	Above 1000 crore	746030.36	37%	3169344.73	78%	3915375.09	64%
Total		2019422.67	100%	4072981.72	100%	6092404.4	100

Source : MCA, MIB, March 2018.

In the case of total share capital range wise the public companies contributions were 40,72,981.72 (Rs in Crores) 67%. Out of this 31,69,344.73 (Rs in Crore) 78% of public companies fallen in the above 1000 crore share capital range and remaining 22% of public companies were falls in the other capital ranges. In the case total share capital range wise

the total companies contributions were 60,92,404.40 (Rs in Crores) 100%. Out of this 3915375.09 (Rs in Crore) 64% of total companies fallen in the above 1000 crore share capital range and remaining 34% of total companies were falls in the other capital ranges.

The above table 9 shows that the totally 18,153 one person companies (OPCs) registered with authorized share capital of (Rs in lakh) 46,106.63 in India as on 30.06.2018. The highest number of one person companies (OPCs) registered India in services sectors totally 15,679 (87%) with authorized share capital (Rs. in lakh) 37634.13 (82%) as on 30.06.2018. Out of this business services sectors registered majority of one person companies (OPCs) 11,613 (65%) with authorized share capital of (Rs. in lakh) 26,086.53 (57%) and community

and social services sectors 1,908 (7%), Trading Sectors 1,296 (2%) and transport and storages sectors 420 (2%) one person companies registered in India. Industrial sectors totally 2,211 (12%) one person companies (OPCs) registered. In this sector, manufacturing 1,385 (8%), Construction 706 (4%), Electricity, Gas and water 75 and mining and quarrying 45 One Person Companies (OPCs) registered in India. Agricultural sectors totally 261(1%) of One Person Companies (OPCs) in India as on 30.06.2018.

Foreign companies registered and active as on 30.06.2018

Table 10 Foreign companies registered and active as on 30 -06-2018

S No	Financial year	Registered	Active
1	Upto 31-03-2013	-	3,240
2	2013-14	216	3,306
3	2014-15	157	3,314
4	2015-16	149	3,336
5	2016-17	160	3,361
6	2017-18	134	3,372
7	2018 - June 18*	25*	3,379*

Source : MCA, MIB, June 2018.

The above table 10 clearly shows that the total number of foreign companies in India 3,240 as on 31-03-2013. In the 2013-14 totally 216 new foreign companies registered and end with totally 3,306 active companies in India as on 31.03.2014. During the 2014-15 totally 157 new foreign companies registered ending with 31.03.2015 totally 3,314 companies were functioning in India. In the year 2015-16 totally ending with 3,336 active foreign companies in India. This period totally 149 foreign companies were registered. During the financial year 2016-17 totally 160 new foreign company registered ending with 3,361 active foreign companies in India as on 31.03.2017. In the year of 2017-18 totally 134 new foreign companies were registered ending with 3,372 foreign companies active as on 31.03.2018. During 01.04.2018 to 30.06.2018 totally 25 new foreign companies registered in India end with totally 3,379 foreign companies are active in India as on 30.06.2018. This study results indicated that ever financial year

more than hundreds of new foreign companies registered in India.

Conclusion

This study finally concluded that growth of private, public government foreign and other type of companies in India after independence is growing staidly and positively. It is indicates that government of India, State/ Union governments and other regulators agencies regulated and implemented effectively in many incentives for companies birth to winding up. Major important economic reform after the independence like implementing new Companies Act 2013 and GST Act 2017 carried out by the government has draw attention to on creating an investor friendly environment. In this technological innovations and developments all over the world, India corporate sectors also changing its old traditional methods services into online methods services to its users at

Sectors-Wise One Person Companies (OPCs) as on 30.06.2018

Table 9 Sector Wise One Person Companies (OPCs) as on 30.06.2018

S No	Sectors	Total Number of (OPCs)	%	Collective Authorized Capital (Rs in lakh)	%
I	Agricultural sectors	261	1	926.3	2
II	Industry	2,211	12	7,516.20	16
1	Manufacturing	1,385	8	4,351.35	9
2	Construction	706	4	2,757.35	6
3	Electricity, Gas & Water	75	0	273.5	1
4	Mining & Quarrying	45	0	134	0
III	Services	15,679	87	37,634.13	82
1	Business Services	11,613	65	26,086.53	57
2	Community & Social Services	1,908	11	4,614.23	10
3	Trading	1,296	7	3,867.92	8
4	Real Estate and Renting	371	2	1,327.30	3
5	Transport and storage	420	2	1,163.15	3
6	Finance	69	0	555	1
7	Insurance	2	0	20	0
IV	Others	2	0	30	0
Total		18,153	100	46,106.63	100

Source : MCA, MIB, June 2018 .

global standards like MCA21 E-Governance project. It will create positive goodwill for starting a new business for domestic and foreign investors.

This study finally suggested that government of India, State/ Union governments, policy framing intuitions and other regulators agencies should improve existing corporate policies, reforms and create new infrastructure in easy doing business

indicators for Indian and foreign investors on regulation for starting a business like land acquisition, dealing with various laws permits, getting electricity and manpower, registering property, getting loans, subsidies, interest free loans and advance, protecting investors investments, improving various direct and indirect tax management system. The government also revised and strengthened various existing laws related to corporate sector, enacted various new amendments and passed new law for strengthening the Indian corporate sectors. This has brought into considerable transparency in the paradigm of corporate regulation and oversight in the country.

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